

NOTES

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**Search for Potential Antiviral Drugs.
Part I. Synthesis of Substituted
Butyrophenone Thiosemicarbazones**

VINAY S. MISRA* and SHIV PRAKASH

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow,
Lucknow.

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ANTI-viral activity of thiosemicarbazones has been confirmed by many workers¹⁻⁹. *In vitro* inhibition of APR-8 and vaccinia viruses has been claimed for a few biphenyl derivatives^{1,0}. Moreover, propiophenones have been shown to exert viricidal effect against Ranikhet disease virus in chlorioallantoic membrane^{1,1}.

A few newer thiosemicarbazones incorporating the active biphenyl moiety have now been synthesised with a view to study their antiviral properties.

4-(4'-Acetamidophenyl)- γ -substituted piperazinyl butyrophenones (I) were obtained by condensing N-substituted piperazines with 4-(4'-Acetamidophenyl)- γ -chloro butyrophenone.

Thiosemicarbazones (II) described in this communication were obtained by treating the butyrophenones (I) with appropriate N-aryl thiosemicarbazides.

Experimental

All the melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

(A) *p*-(*p*-Acetamidophenyl)- γ -substituted piperazinyl-butyrophenones :

A mixture of *p*-(*p*-acetamidophenyl)- γ -chloro-butyrophenone (.02 mole), an appropriate piperazine^{1,1,1,2} (.02 mole) was refluxed in absolute ethanol for 24 hrs. At the end of this period the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue treated several times with hot water. The crude product so obtained was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

R, m. p. and other data are recorded in Table 1.

S. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	%N	
					Calcd	Found
1.	-CH ₃	152	65	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ N ₃ O ₂	11.08	10.98
2.	-Ph	148	60	C ₂₈ H ₃₁ N ₃ O ₂	9.52	9.44
3.	-(CH ₂) ₂ Ph	170	61	C ₂₉ H ₃₃ N ₃ O ₂	9.23	9.12

(B) *p*-(*p*-Acetamidophenyl)- γ -substituted piperazinyl butyrophenone thiosemicarbazones :

A solution of *p*-(*p*-Acetamidophenyl)- γ substituted piperazinyl butyrophenone (.002 mole) in ethanol (containing one drop of conc. HCl) was mixed with the solution of appropriate aryl thiosemicarbazide^o (.002 mole) in ethanol and the mixture was refluxed for 6-8 hrs. After concentration and cooling a solid mass separated out which was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

R, R', m. p. and other data are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Sl No	R	R'	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	%N	
					Calcd	Found
1.	-CH ₃	H	179	C ₃₀ H ₃₈ N ₆ OS	15.99	15.54
2.	-CH ₃	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	182	C ₃₁ H ₃₈ N ₆ OS	15.50	15.28
3.	-CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	190	C ₃₁ H ₃₈ N ₆ OS	15.50	15.12
4.	-CH ₃	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	192	C ₃₁ H ₃₉ N ₆ O ₂ S	15.05	14.64
5.	-CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	185	C ₃₁ H ₃₉ N ₆ O ₂ S	15.05	14.56
6.	-Ph	-H	176	C ₃₅ H ₃₈ N ₆ OS	14.23	13.98
7.	-Ph	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	152	C ₃₈ H ₄₀ N ₆ OS	13.90	13.48
8.	-Ph	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	165	C ₃₈ H ₄₀ N ₆ OS	13.90	13.62
9.	-Ph	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	185	C ₃₈ H ₄₀ N ₆ O ₂ S	13.55	13.26
10.	-Ph	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	179	C ₃₈ H ₄₀ N ₆ O ₂ S	13.55	13.18
11.	-(CH ₂) ₂ Ph	H	195	C ₃₈ H ₄₀ N ₆ OS	13.33	13.24
12.	-(CH ₂) ₂ Ph	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	200	C ₃₇ H ₄₂ N ₆ OS	13.04	12.94
13.	-(CH ₂) ₂ Ph	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	210	C ₃₇ H ₄₂ N ₆ OS	13.04	12.88
14.	-(CH ₂) ₂ Ph	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	185	C ₃₇ H ₄₂ N ₆ O ₂ S	12.72	12.46
15.	-(CH ₂) ₂ Ph	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	215	C ₃₇ H ₄₂ N ₆ O ₂ S	12.72	12.54

These compounds were obtained in 60-70% yield.

Bioassay

Antiviral activity was determined by the method of Dhar et al^{1,6}. Surprisingly none of the compounds exhibited appreciable antiviral activity against Ranikhet disease (heavy R N A) and vaccinia (house D N A) viruses at the dose of .01 mg/ml in cell cultures (C A M cultures or C E F Mono layers).

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